

An Appreciation of the Career of Nina Thornhill

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Abstract: David Bogle is the Pro-Vice-Provost of the Doctoral School at University College London (UCL). He is the Deputy Director of the Centre of Process Systems Engineering and the Scientific Vice President of the European Federation of Chemical Engineers. David joined the Chemical Engineering Department at UCL in 1990 and has followed and promoted Nina Thornhill's career for nearly three decades.

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I have been working with Nina for almost thirty years! When I first came to UCL in 1990 I became part of the Centre for Process Systems Engineering (CPSE) straight away – it was natural since my PhD had been in the PSE group at Imperial College – and Nina was also involved from within Electrical Engineering at UCL. Nina led the Major Project in Biological Processes within CPSE (in collaboration with UCL Biochemical Engineering) and I took this over when she went on sabbatical to BP. At the time Nina was working on fermentation control building on her ICI Control Engineering experience. Although we had no joint students we did share experiences even after the Biological Processes project finished.

As others have mentioned she spent some time in Alberta and with ABB. This latter relationship grew into an application for a Royal Academy of Engineering/ABB chair, which she took up at Imperial College within CPSE and Chemical Engineering. The move seemed a natural one as she had been shifting even more into chemical process control and, more significantly, into process automation. While there are many academic groups working in process control there are few in process automation which brings together control, advanced instrumentation, statistical use of data, and the more complex aspects of operations management for improved profitability, safety and environmental performance.

Canada was a notable exception with several process automation groups and her time there was significant. This whole area has now become a much higher priority across the process industries as 'Smart Process Manufacturing' or 'Industry 4.0'. This has been enabled by the huge increase in data availability together with developments in Process

Systems Engineering, in advanced statistics and in measurement. It is also enabling the development of flexible processes for integrated and agile supply chains. Nina was ahead of this trend.

For its research chairs the Royal Academy appoints one of its fellows as a mentor and I was asked to be Nina's mentor. The role is to support and suggest as well as to challenge the host institution and sponsors. Nina has made very significant contributions, both theoretical and practical, in this area of process automation. I would like to see it have a greater part in the undergraduate curriculum, which is dominated by fundamentals and design, largely because of the practical difficulties involved in running complex operational pedagogical projects even on simulations. Her pedagogical interest was clear and she followed me as external examiner for the Process Automation MSc at Newcastle University. She attracted the course down to Imperial and took on the role of Programme co-Director. The course has strong industrial support with candidates doing it part time alongside industrial positions. The research projects use new principles applied in industrial practice. She has also been active on the Process Control and Automation Special Interest Group of the Institution of Chemical Engineers.

Nina's research contributions and the impact they have had on process automation practice in ABB and elsewhere were recognized through her election as Fellow of the Royal Academy of Engineering in 2009. She has undoubtedly been a UK pioneer in academic process automation bringing rigour and innovation to both theory and practice. The PSE community will miss her. We wish her a long and fruitful retirement.